

HISTORICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF READING CULTURE IN FAMILIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18997417>

Abstract. *In society, the book serves as a means of social communication. Analyzing the historical foundations of the processes related to the use, preservation, and organization of reading, as well as their consistent continuation in modern practice, and drawing scientific conclusions based on this analysis is considered one of the pressing issues of today. The work carried out in this area represents a significant step in matters of child upbringing within the family and strengthening family unity. This article scientifically substantiates the impact of family reading on the family environment by analyzing the scholarly views of our historical thinkers alongside the scientific conclusions of contemporary educators. Based on scientific analysis, conclusions, proposals, and recommendations aimed at developing family reading culture have been formulated.*

Keywords: *family, community (mahalla), pedagogy, reading, book, readership, parents, child, reading culture, scholar, family reading, society.*

Introduction

In the historical development of New Uzbekistan, books and their dissemination through information-library systems and librarianship constitute an integral part of human culture. Throughout the processes of cultural and historical continuity, books and libraries serve as unparalleled tools for maintaining connections among people, linking the present with the past and future, and acting as a vital link in the spiritual connection between generations and ancestors. As a means of social communication in society, information-library institutions, which organize the storage and reading of books, play a significant role in educating students, developing their thinking, enhancing IQ levels, guiding them toward professional activities, and helping them mature into independent individuals. Due to advances in science and technology, the volume of information is increasing day by day. As a result, new responsibilities are being placed on library professionals. One of these responsibilities is to provide fast and comprehensive information to consumers-school students, teaching staff, and the general public-through information technologies.

Information culture is a broad concept that has been defined differently by various scholars. In particular, A. Ibragimov describes information culture as the skill to effectively use all available information tools in everyday life and professional activities. Modern computer technologies greatly assist users in providing, analyzing, teaching, and reprocessing information, and in the future, they will play an essential role in developing highly skilled and competent specialists. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 15, 2026, No. PQ-9, “On measures to develop reading culture and promote interest in reading among the population,” elevates the establishment of a “Reading Society” to the level of State policy and recognizes it as

one of the most important tasks in the information age. The decree sets the goal of raising the average annual number of books read per person to 10 between 2026 and 2030.

Furthermore, the Presidential Order dated January 12, 2017, on “Establishing a Commission to develop the system of publishing and distributing books, promote reading, and improve reading culture” is significant as it aimed to comprehensively address the challenges in this area. A special working group developed a comprehensive program of measures to improve book publishing and distribution, promote reading, and enhance reading culture. Subsequently, Presidential Decree No. 3271 was adopted in September of the same year. This process emphasizes popularizing reading, introducing children and youth to books, encouraging reading in the country’s libraries, developing book readership and book trade, preparing and enhancing the qualifications of personnel in the field, improving the system, and monitoring reading habits.

The emergence of the book is directly linked to the advent of writing. Indeed, after humanity discovered writing, people sought to record their thoughts and, ultimately, to share their life experiences and principles with others, as well as to compare their ideas with those of others. Unsurprisingly, these tendencies contributed to the miracle of the book’s creation. In ancient Egypt, Greece, and Central Asia, people initially recorded their thoughts on materials such as stone, palm leaves, and similar media. Historical evidence shows that after ideas and thoughts began to be written on papyrus, scroll books started to appear. People even inscribed their reflections on clay, though these early writings were quite heavy.

As human thinking and standards of living developed, the “weight” of books began to decrease-both literally and figuratively-because a characteristic feature of humanity is the continual pursuit of perfection, refinement, and convenience. “The peoples of Turan adopted the advanced achievements of Ancient Asia, Greece, Egypt, India, and other regions in writing and librarianship. This, in turn, led to the copying of books in manuscript form and the establishment of libraries in Central Asia.”

Although many rare books were preserved in Central Asia, the destruction of libraries by invaders led to a significant cultural decline. Books are essential for valuing faith, understanding one’s identity, and recognizing the Truth. For this reason, today in our country, great efforts have been made to publish and distribute religious and educational books, as well as the guidance works of our great scholars. This process has been carried out consistently, including the establishment of specialized publishing houses and limited liability companies dedicated to religious literature.

The works of eminent scholars and spiritual leaders such as Imam Bukhari, Termeziy, Rumi, and Yassavi-including guidance books, collections of hadith commentaries, and other writings-now fill the shelves of bookstores. Gratitude for these achievements is certainly deserved. By consulting these books, we can find detailed, well-supported answers to questions about the true nature of Islam, its purpose, and its history. These books serve as a guiding light in the darkness. Through their study, we can avoid superstition, heretical practices, and sinful actions. Additionally, reading these authentic and reliable works helps us understand sacred concepts such as parents, homeland, and nation. For these reasons, the importance of such educational works is immense.

The discovery of paper not only made book production more convenient but also fostered the art of decoration and binding. Calligraphy and bookbinding flourished in the Middle Ages. We know from history notable calligraphers such as Sultan Ali Mashhadi. Many rare manuscripts copied by Sultan Ali Mashhadi have survived to our time. Enhancing ink with fragrances and rose water, or writing with gold ink, made books aesthetically pleasing as well as meaningful.

In the palaces of enlightened rulers, special scribes and calligraphers worked, creating vast libraries filled with rare books. A remarkable tradition of presenting books as gifts emerged among kings and sultans, with books being regarded as the finest presents. For example, historical sources report that one of the sultans gifted Mirzo Ulughbek with several volumes of works by Khusraw Dehlavi. When Prince Abdullatif received news of the approaching caravan and hastened to intercept it, he opened the chests only to discover, not the rare gold and jewels he had expected, but a chest full of thick books.

This issue has been interpreted in the context of folk pedagogy, Islamic literature, and the teachings of great thinkers, emphasizing intellectual development and the pursuit of knowledge. The educational and moral views of scholars such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, Yusuf Khas Hajib, Kaykavus, Ahmad Yugnaki, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Husayn Voiz Kashifi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, and later Abdulla Avloni and Abdurauf Fitrat clearly demonstrate the role of books in learning and acquiring knowledge.

Abu Rayhan al-Biruni emphasized that human character is primarily formed within the family environment. The scholar advises parents to maintain a balanced approach to their child's psychological state. He also encourages parents to provide children with what is desirable and beneficial for them while keeping them away from things that may be harmful. According to al-Biruni, parents' consistent and uniform behavior toward a child is crucial for proper upbringing. Conversely, inconsistent treatment can create conditions for the development of negative traits in the child's character.

Al-Biruni links human moral qualities and ethical concepts directly to human nature, which is first shaped within the family. Therefore, the influence of parents and their exemplary behavior is of paramount importance in child-rearing. For instance, he advises women through the words of Abdulla ibn Jafar: "Avoid jealousy, for it is the key to divorce. I forbid you from frequently reprimanding your husband, as it breeds hatred. Maintain your appearance, using suitable means. Also, make use of pleasant scents; the best among them is water." These instructions are directly related to raising children within the family. Al-Biruni also addresses physical and spiritual purity. Where cleanliness, order, and hygiene exist in the household, spiritual purity will also be present. This concept goes beyond maintaining a clean body; it encourages active engagement and effort, which is associated with labor and productivity. His ideas on the unity of the body and soul's purity reflect the connection between physical health and moral-spiritual development, aligning with contemporary understanding of balanced child upbringing.

He further notes that inconsistent parental behavior leads to varied traits in children. Al-Biruni scientifically argued that balanced child behavior ensures both physical and mental well-being. He emphasized that in child development, heredity, environment, and upbringing are equally important. Al-Biruni approached moral education based on the principles of Islam, viewing morality as emerging and developing from the struggle between good and evil. His perspective was both innovative and scientifically prophetic for his time.

Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi, in his works, divided parents into two categories: the biological father, responsible for the child's physical creation and growth, and the educational (spiritual) father, responsible for the child's full moral and intellectual development. He emphasized that considering both roles in unity is crucial for effective upbringing. His following words are particularly instructive: "I have seen no teacher better than the times and no student better than the human being." From this statement, we understand, on one hand, the decisive

influence of the social environment on child-rearing, and on the other hand, that a human being can achieve perfection through proper education. The issue of the family and child-rearing within the family occupies an important place in the scholarly legacy of Abu Ali Ibn Sina. In his numerous works, he writes extensively about the child's health, upbringing, and, most importantly, the study of the child's psychological development. His insights form a coherent system of pedagogical views aimed at shaping a morally and spiritually well-rounded individual. In Ibn Sina's work *Tadbiri al-manozil*, a large chapter is devoted specifically to the family and issues of family education.

From the views of the aforementioned scholars, philosophers, psychologists, pedagogues, philologists, and literary scholars, it is clear that the family is considered a sacred institution. They emphasize the need to cultivate reading habits within the family as a means to elevate its moral values and advance its cultural development. These scholars concluded that "books remain dead until they are revived through the individuality of the reader. Each new reader discovers a new text within the same work." The study of reading culture and the development of family reading habits in Uzbekistan during the years of independence has expanded opportunities to analyze how contemporary pedagogy can be shaped. This is based on the research of numerous philologists, pedagogues, psychologists, and historians, who have highlighted the importance of reading, as well as how family literacy contributes to the spiritual and cultural wealth of the household.

O.A.Turakulova analyzed technologies for forming and developing reading culture in students through literature lessons, including methodological and pedagogical-psychological approaches, classroom and extracurricular activities, and the effectiveness of project-based learning. K.A.Abdulvahidov, in his scholarly articles, explores the social and philosophical foundations of reading culture. Sayyora Chiniyeva, in her publications, provides analytical conclusions on how reading together with children in the family and cultivating a reading culture enhances their intellectual abilities, worldview, and spiritual maturity.

Reading and discussing books together in a family environment fosters the development of thought and requires active participation from both parents. These studies emphasize the social and pedagogical significance of cultivating a culture of reading within the family. D. Davronova notes that "by fostering the social awareness of minors within the family and contributing to the development of the 'Family-Neighborhood-Educational Institution' cooperation system, it is possible to advance the educational framework and address issues of family upbringing through enhancing children's social consciousness." She pays particular attention to this issue and, drawing on the views and research of foreign scholars on the development of social awareness, highlights the advantages of establishing cooperation between the family, neighborhood, and educational institutions. Research by both local and international scholars shows that it is unfortunate when parents in today's families consider fostering children's interest in books and reading solely the responsibility of the teacher.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present a number of recommendations for promoting a culture of reading within families:

A variety of methods can be used to develop and cultivate reading skills in children. To foster interest and motivation in reading, it is recommended to organize book festivals, engaging meetings with children who have achieved high results in reading, and local young poets, as well as use inspiring video clips and stories.

Roundtable discussions, analysis of famous works, question-and-answer reading sessions, and thinking exercises in a training format help children develop skills in understanding and analyzing texts. In the family setting, real reading activities can be organized through keeping a book diary, small theatrical performances, discussion evenings, and book fairs.

To engage children through community collaboration, organizing trips to the local Cultural and Leisure Center positively impacts them. A library that is cozy, bright, and has a pleasant and calm atmosphere is appealing to children. Introducing the environment of books by library staff sparks curiosity and interest. Non-traditional exhibitions in the library allow children to interact freely with books. Organizing a “Describe My Favorite Book” activity encourages children to name and describe the books they enjoy. This process develops the child’s ability to classify books, construct small sentences based on the content, creatively describe, make conscious choices, analyze the selected work briefly, think independently, and develop communication skills while sharing their descriptions, making the activity more meaningful. At the conclusion, active participants were awarded certificates.

Children develop cognitive skills, critical thinking, teamwork, and communication abilities.

Meetings titled “My Reading Peer” in neighborhoods, where children who have achieved success in local reading activities are invited, generate great interest not only among children but also among parents. Organizing reading competitions at the district or city level, recognizing the winners, and involving the “hero” of the event creates a strong impression on peers. Young participants who achieve success through reading are warmly welcomed at their schools and among their peers. Their experiences emphasize the importance of effort, self-confidence, and support from parents and relatives, inspiring other children in the community to become avid readers.

Short video clips showcasing children who have achieved high results in national competitions stimulate interest, enthusiasm, and aspirations for achievement among children, while also motivating parents. Parents, understanding that responsibility and initiative are essential for their child’s success, realize the importance of being role models and actively promoting family reading habits.

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